

The Relationship between Tax Avoidance and Bank Costs of Debt Case Study: Accepted Companies in Tehran Stock Exchange

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Akram Afshar ⁽²⁾Ali Bayat ⁽³⁾Kamran Yeganegi

⁽¹⁾Department of Accounting, Islamic Azad University, Qazvin Branch, Qazvin, Iran ⁽²⁾Department of Accounting, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan Branch, Zanjan, Iran ⁽³⁾Department of Industrial Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan Branch, Zanjan, Iran

Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the relationship between tax avoidance and costs of debt of accepted companies in Tehran Stock Exchange. Regarding essence and purpose, this study is applied which can be used by Tax Affairs Organization, Financial managers of companies, banks, universities, higher education centers, researchers, and a wide range of users. Regarding research method, this research is the descriptive-analytic type of correlation regression analysis. Since this study examines the extant relationships between variables and data are collected from the environment which has naturally existed or the past events which have occurred without direct interference of the researcher, it is post-event research and is based on panel data analysis. In this study, financial information of 67 accepted companies in Tehran Stock Exchange has been investigated during the period of 2005 to 2015. To analyze the obtained results from the research, SPSS 20 and Eviews 7 have been used. Results of the study show that increasing cost of debt, level of tax avoidance (temporary tax disputes, the effective rate of tax liability, and effective rate of long-term tax liability) also increases.
Keywords: Cost, Bank debt, Tax avoidance, Tehran Stock Exchange

1. Introduction

Stock exchange as an organized market provides required facilities for buyers and sellers of stock so that they can change their money into securities or vice versa. Since the stock exchange is proposed as an organization to equip and direct the savings toward productive and useful investments for society and economy of the country, it is particularly important to study and research on this organization (Parsaeian & Jahankhani, 1996).

One of the main instruments to develop and deepen the capital market is an improvement of analysis level in this market. Without extensive and comprehensive research and analyses in the capital market, it cannot be expected that its position grows in the national economy. A brief investigation of evolution process of Tehran Stock Exchange as the main foundation of the organized capital market in Iran economy shows that an analysis gap had been dominant in this market. However, within recent years, promising steps have been taken to take advantage of global indices and standards to analyze capital market of our country. However, we have a long distance to the optimal and perfect condition of analysis level in the capital market, and there is a widespread space to work in this field (Sadeghi Zanjani & Vafadar, 2005).

One of the basic assumptions in financial management literature is that each company is formed to maximize the wealth of its shareholders and to achieve the mentioned goal, company management should pay attention to the factors of outflow and expenditure of cash in decision making. Income tax on the company will decrease future earnings of the company. Therefore, one of the steps can be taken to maximize the value of the company and wealth of the shareholders is the use of approaches through which tax paid of company decreases. One of the reasons which companies do activities of tax avoidance is debt substitution characteristic (Lim, 2011). In other words, saving corporate taxes which are derived from tax avoidance activities can be used for financing company projects.

2. Tax Avoidance

In most of the countries, the main part of government revenue source is provided through tax. The share of total public revenues varies among countries. In the meantime, tax avoidance has caused that tax revenue of countries is less than what has always been estimated. Therefore, one of the most important topics which are currently being considered in most research studies is the tax avoidance discussion, factors affecting it, and consequences which result from it. Theoretically, tax avoidance means trying to reduce tax paid (Hanlon et al.,

2010). Tax evasion is a kind of legal evasion, but tax avoidance is, in fact, a kind of use of legal vacuum in tax laws to reduce taxes. So since tax avoidance is apparently a legal activity, it seems that it is exposed to be more seen than tax evasion. In addition, since tax avoidance is within the defined limits for using tax benefits and there are generally no rules on tax avoidance control (Jam, 2000); therefore, it seems that many companies involve in tax avoidance, due to this determination of affecting factors on level of tax avoidance in companies are very important.

It seems that tax avoidance topic to be proposed on companies with separation of ownership because real people due to the probability of detection, fining, risk aversion or internal motives like social duty are less involved in tax evasion and avoidance (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972). But in companies, typically, shareholders expect executives to pursue their own interests, and as long as the additional benefits resulting from the reduction of possible debt are more than the expected additional costs to them, they pursue the reduction of tax debt and avoidance. So tax avoidance can be a reflection of representative theory, and it might result in tax decisions which follow the personal benefits of the manager. Therefore, one of the challenges faced by shareholders and the board of directors is finding control methods and incentives to minimize the costs of representative (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Desai et al. (2007) also believe that managers who seek their personal benefits make the structure of company more complex and carry out the deals which reduce tax and through this use the benefits of the company for their personal interests. They believe that the presence of strong tax officers causes an increase of monitoring on work of managers and reduction of misuse of internal resources of the corporation. Another point which was proposed by Desai et al. is that governing and leadership of companies influence tax avoidance level of companies. Weak corporate governance leads to increase in tax avoidance level. Graham (2006) believes that tax avoidance decreases the final benefits of tax shield and it might affect decisions related to the structure of invest. On the other hand, if tax avoidance is detected by tax officials, in this case, the company will have to pay extra pays and fines which cause reduction of cash entry flows and wealth of shareholders.

Another viewpoint which proposed on tax avoidance is that despite separation of control from ownership, tax avoidance phenomenon can be valuable and if the owners can create the necessary motivational backgrounds in the managers in order they make effective decisions with appropriate tax planning, value of the company will increase and consequently shareholder wealth will increase (Hanlon et. al, 2010).

2.1 The difference of Tax Evasion and Tax Avoidance

The conceptual distinction between tax evasion and tax avoidance is related to legality or illegality of payers' behavior. Tax evasion is a kind of law violation. When a taxpayer refuses to provide a proper report on his earned income or capital which include tax payments, he does an unofficial action which keeps him out of the eyes of government and tax officials. But in tax avoidance, the individual is not worried about disclosing his actions (Maleki, 2013).

Tax avoidance derives from legal gaps in tax laws. Here, the individual seeks ways to escape in order to reduce the ability to pay taxation. For example, taxpayer indicates that income of labor as capital income which includes lower tax rate. In tax avoidance, there is no reason that the payer is worried about the probability of disclosing because he necessarily writes and records all of his transactions with their details of course in unreal form (Maleki, 2013).

Indeed, economic agents attempt to reduce their tax debt using tax law gaps and revision in their economic decisions. Since tax avoidance is seemingly legal, it is more likely than tax evasion to be exposed.

In other words, tax avoidance is a formal misuse of tax laws. This category is related to investigating and finding escape ways from taxpayers in tax regulations by which taxpayers exclude themselves from individuals included tax payment. For example, the exchange of labor income for capital income which leads to a lower rate of tax is an example of tax avoidance. For an illustration, suppose that value-added tax is placed on an activity like bike sale. Now, if one seller sells fewer bicycles for less tax, his behavior is based on tax avoidance. If the

same seller reports the amount of bicycle sale less than its real amount to tax organization, his behavior will be regarded tax evasion.

Therefore, tax avoidance is legal and is to reduce the tax liability of an individual through bypassing the law or making full use of legal aspects, but tax evasion is illegal and is to embark intentionally on illegal acts like unrealistic reports of income and sale, deductions and adjustments of declarations. The tax system, in ideal conditions, must be able to deal with both types of tax evasion.

2.2 Background of Tax Evasion Emergence

Different investigations show that the most widespread backgrounds of tax evasion emergence are as following (Asadi et al., 2012):

- a- Non-propagation of tax culture in society: Tax culture is a set of attitude, vision, and reaction of individuals against tax system. In other words, attitudes, insights, perceptions, aspirations, social values, current laws, and the level of education and awareness are among the factors that shape tax culture.
- b- Lack of full information exchange and monitoring and tracking system in tax collection
- c- Estimated assessment and presentation of weakness in it
- d- Lack of tax returns submission and weakness in executive guarantees

There are a variety of reasons for not submitting tax returns. The most common reason for non-submission can be that, if there is no up-to-date record of the payer, the best opportunity to submit a tax return and escape tax payment is provided. Another reason is lack of decisive confrontation of tax officers which can be due to lack of familiarization or enough command of tax officers to tax laws and having not enough skill in performing them.

- e- Delay in tax collection.
- f- Lack of recognizing taxpayers and the lack of documentation of their income.
- g- Presence of extensive and divers exemptions:

Sometimes governments open the way of tax evasion by adopting supportive tax policies and tax exemptions. In addition, if there is not also an effective information system in the tax system, tax evasion increases. Also granting tax exemptions, some groups are exempted from taxation, and this leads to a reduction in government tax revenues. Therefore, if tax exemptions grants do not perform attentively, the government will put heavy pressure on other groups of society to earn taxable income. It means in order to compensate empty part of tax revenue; more tax rates will be imposed on the groups which do not benefit from tax exemptions. Undoubtedly, granting widespread tax exemptions leads to inefficiencies in the tax system and the weakness of the tax administration system.

3. Research Background

●In their research, Rego and Wilson (2015) addressed to granting reward to financial manager and CEO and deceptive tax reports and its relationship with company's future performance. They concluded that there is a positive relationship between reward and deceptive tax reporting.

●Blouin et al. (2014) examined that whether tax avoidance planning can reduce organizational complexity and clarity of financial reporting. They resulted that increasing tax avoidance planning, the level of analysts' predictive errors of tax avoidance planning and dispersion of predictions will increase while the quality of guaranteed items of incorporation decreases. Additionally, the results of their research showed that managers are trying to reduce the effect of tax avoidance planning to increase the volume of disclosing in financial statements.

●In their study, Desai, Duck, and Zingales (2013) resulted that high tax rates cause corporate governance systems to worsen, in contrast; low tax rates cause corporate governance systems to improve and will follow tax income increase.

●Harrington and Smith (2012) showed that whether using long-term debt in structure of investment influence tax avoidance or not using effective tax rate index (the ratio of tax expense to interest before tax): corporates which use more debts in their investment structure have a higher financial leverage, and tax avoidance in these kinds of companies is higher than companies which have lower financial leverage in their investment structure.

In Table 1, a summary of research studies on this has presented.

Table.1

A summary of conducted research studies

Author	Year	Research Title	Summary of Results
Rego and Wilson	2015	An investigation of granting a bonus to financial manager and CEO and deceptive tax reports and its relationship with corporates performance in future	There is a positive relationship between bonus and deceptive tax reporting.
Blouin et. al	2014	An Investigation of Reduction of Organizational Aggressiveness and Transparency of financial reporting by tax avoidance planning	Increasing Tax Avoidance Planning Level, Analysts Prediction Error and Prediction Dispersion Will Increase Simultaneously.
Desai, Duck, and Zingales	2013	An Investigation of Tax Rate by Corporate Governance System	high tax rates cause corporate governance systems to worsen, in contrast; low tax rates cause corporate governance systems to improve and will follow tax income increase
Harrington and Smith	2012	The Effect of Long-term Debt on Capital Structure	Corporates which use more debts in their investment structure have higher financial leverage, and tax avoidance in these kinds of companies is higher than companies which have lower financial leverage in their investment structure.
Armstrong et. al	2011	Explaining Effective Incentive on Tax Planning	There is a negative and significant relationship between incentive bonus schemes for tax managers with

			effective calculated tax rate based on accounting standards, but there is a weak relationship between mentioned scheme and other used criteria.	
Dyreng et. al	2010	Using Effective Long-run Cash Tax Rates to Measure Tax Avoidance Level of Corporates Over 10 Years	There is a significant cross-sectional variation incorporates tax avoidance, and about 25 percent of corporations are able to maintain effective cash tax rate under 20 percent.	
Dogan et. al	2007	An Investigation of Relationship between Profitability, Company Size and Financial Risk with Timeliness of Reporting for Active Companies on the International Exchange	Profitable corporates are more interested in providing financial reporting faster than unprofitable corporates.	
Long Chen and Xinlei Zhao	2006	An Investigation of Relationship between Market Value to Book Value and Debt Ratios	Contrary to popular belief, corporates which have high market value to book value also have high debt ratios.	
Eugene Nivorozhkin	2005	The Study of the Capital Structure of Eastern European Countries	The average ratio of debt to the salary of shareholders in these countries over time tends towards Western European countries and tend to approach debt ratios of their Western European neighbors.	

Campbell Harvey et. al	2004	Does Debt Can Modify the Effects of Agency or Information Problems or not?	Debt increases environmental investment opportunities for corporate.
Turan Orwell	2003	Investigating the Effects of Corporate Debt on Products Pricing in Developing Countries	First, current debts increase the price of the product, and long-term debt reduces the price of the product. Current debt has a cyclical impact on the price of products of corporate
Donald Boschart	2003	An Assessment of Nature of Optimal Capital Structure and Investment in Economy in Which the Role of Government in Providing Public Goods	In such economies, neither the maximization of value for the optimal capital structure would be regarded as the ultimate goal of the company.
Fernandes et. al	2001	Capital Structure in the World Airline Industry	Airline companies highly need to finance in these companies, the company's capital is at least 40% of the total funds which are used in its current operations.
Greg Filbeck and Raymond Gorman	2000	Capital structure and asset utilization: the case of resource-intensive industries	The more companies increase effective use of their assets, the more their leverage ratios increase.

4. Results of the Study

Following models were used in this study:

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 BTE_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 ETR_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 CETR_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 LETR_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 LCETR_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

Type of Variable	Variable	Symbol of Variable	Calculation
Independent	Effective Tax Rate	ETR	$\frac{\text{income tax expenses}}{\text{earnings (or income earned) before taxes}}$
Independent	Cash Effective Tax Rate	CETR	$\frac{\text{Cash tax paid}}{\text{earnings (or income earned) before taxes}}$
Independent	Book Tax Differences	BTD	$\frac{\text{instrumental tax} - \text{Tax according to the discovery sheet}}{\text{Total assets of the first period}}$
Independent	Long- run Effective Tax Rate	LETR	$\frac{\text{Total tax income over three years}}{\text{sum of earnings (or income earned) before taxes in the same period}}$
Independent	Long- run Cash Effective Tax Rate	LCETR	$\frac{\text{Total of cash tax paid over three years}}{\text{total of earnings (or income earned) before taxes in the same period}}$
Dependent	Cost Liability	CBL	$\frac{\text{benefit cost}}{\text{debts with interest}}$
Control	Corporate Size	SIZE	The normal logarithm of the total assets of the company
Control	Financial Leverage	LEV	The ratio of long-run debts to a total of assets
Control	Investment Opportunities	MTB	The ration of market value to book value of each share
Control	Sale Growth Rate	SG	The ratio of current year sale difference with last year to the sale of last year

4-1 Testing Research Hypotheses

4-1-1 Testing the First Research Hypothesis

The first research hypothesis was stated as follows:

“There is a positive relationship between temporary tax difference and debt expense.”

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 BTD_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

Regarding the results of the table, research model has heterogeneity of variance problem. Therefore, the generalized least squares method should be used to test the model. Results from research model test can be seen in Table 3.

Table.3

Results of the First Research Model

EGLS			Variable
Likelihood	Statistics t	Coefficients	
0.000	3.487	0.411	Temporary Tax Difference
0.000	5.790	0.061	Corporate Size
0.000	-11.613	0.113	Financial Leverage
0.000	-3.639	-0.031	Growth and Profitability Opportunities
0.080	2.167	-0.056	Sale Growth Rate
0.001	-3.247	-0.252	Fixed Variable(C)
0.781			Coefficient of determination
0.713			The modified coefficient of determination
1.994			Durbin–Watson statistic
12.674			Statistic F
0.000			Likelihood of statistics F

Results show that temporary tax difference has a direct and significant effect on debt cost of corporate which mentioned relationship is 0.41 based on regression coefficient. In addition, size of corporate and operational leverage has had a direct and significant effect on debt cost of corporate, but the effect of growth opportunities and profitability variables is reverse and significant on debt cost.

Results related to statistic F (0.000) also show that the model is significant in general and Durbin–Watson statistic is also in optimal range. In addition to this, results related to the Modified coefficient of determination indicate that 0.71 of debt cost of corporates has been influenced by temporary tax difference and control variables in research period. Therefore, regarding significance and directness of effect of temporary tax difference on debt cost of corporates, we cannot reject the first hypothesis of this study.

4-1-2 Testing Second Research Hypothesis

The second research hypothesis was stated as follows:

“There is a positive relationship between effective tax rate and debt cost.”

$$CBL_{i,t} = \beta_1 ETR_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 MTB_{i,t} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{i,t} + C_{i,t}$$

Regarding results, research model has heterogeneity of variance problem. Therefore, the generalized least squares method should be used to test the model. Results from research model test can be seen in Table 4.

Table.4

Results of Second Research Model

EGLS			Variable
Likelihood	Statistics	Coefficient	
0.001	3.148	-0.110	Effective Tax Rate
0.000	0.810	-0.090	Size of Corporate
0.013	2.472	-0.031	Financial Leverage
0.040	0.818	0.004	Growth and Profitability Opportunities
0.092	0.122	0.001	Sale Growth Rate
0.138	1.484	0.028	Fixed Variable
0.701			Coefficient of Determination
0.660			The modified coefficient of determination
1.978			Durbin–Watson statistic
17.290			Statistic F
0.000			Statistic Likelihood F

Results show that effective tax rate has had a reverse and significant effect on debt cost of corporates; in addition, size of corporate and financial leverage variables had a reverse, and significant effect on debt cost of corporates, growth and profitability opportunities also has a direct effect on debt cost. In other cases, control variables did not have any significant effect on debt cost.

Results related to statistic F (0.000) show that the model is significant in general and Durbin–Watson statistic is also in the optimal range (1.97). In addition to this, results related to the Modified coefficient of determination indicate that 0.66 of debt cost of corporates have been influenced by effective tax rate and control variables in research period. Therefore, regarding above results, we cannot reject second research hypothesis.

4-1-3 Testing Third Research Hypothesis

The third research hypothesis was stated as follows:

“There is a positive relationship between effective cash tax and debt cost.”

Regarding results of Table 4, research model has heterogeneity of variance problem. Therefore, the generalized least squares method should be used to test the model. Results from research model test can be seen in Table 5.

Table.5

Results of Third Research Model

EGLS			Variable
Likelihood d t	Statistics t	Coefficient	
0.109	-1.603	-0.083	Effective Cash Tax Rate
0.047	2.216	-0.043	Size of Corporate
0.000	-6.596	-0.007	Financial Leverage
0.066	1.839	0.004	Growth and Profitability Opportunities
0.076	-1.088	0.061	Sale Growth Rate
0.049	-1.972	0.209	Fixed Variable (C)
0.645			Coefficient of Determination
0.570			The modified coefficient of determination
2.057			Durbin-Watson statistic
5.917			Statistic F
0.000			Statistic Likelihood F

Results show that effective cash tax rate has had the reverse effect on debt cost of corporates, but the mentioned effect is not significant. Also, growth and profitability opportunities and sale growth rate variables did not have any significant effect on debt cost of corporates. But the size of the company and financial leverage had a reverse and significant effect on effective cash tax rate of corporates.

Results related to statistic F (0.000) also show that the model is significant in general and Durbin–Watson statistic is also in the optimal range (2.05). In addition to this, results related to the Modified coefficient of determination indicate that 0.57 of debt cost of corporates have been influenced by effective cash tax rate and other control variables of corporate in research period. Therefore, regarding above results, we reject third research hypothesis.

5. Summary and Conclusion

Results indicate that there is a direct relationship temporary tax difference and debt cost level so that the higher is the temporary tax difference. Naturally, the higher will be the debt cost of that corporate. Also, effective tax rate had a reverse and significant effect on debt cost of corporates so that increasing effective tax rate, cost debt decreases. Finally, effective cash tax rate has had the reverse effect on debt cost of corporates but mentioned effect was not significant. This means that there is not any significant relationship between debt cost and effective cash tax rate. Results from the above test can be interpreted that information content of accrual items is higher than cash items. Perhaps one of the reasons for above hypothesis rejection is that managers try to use accrual criteria and scales to evaluate corporate in general (for example, use of financial ratios).

6. References

- i. Hassas Yegane Yahya, Golmohammadi Shoraki Mojtaba, Winter 2011. “The Relationship between Effective Tax Rate and Characteristics of Corporates”. *Journal of Tax Research*, No 60.
- ii. Khani Abdollah, Soltani Asfrizi AliReza, August and September 2013. “Aggressive Tax Reporting and Its Relationship with Aggressive Tax Reporting”. *Economic Journal*. No. 5 & 6, pp. 5-16.

- iii. Khajavi Shokrollah, Amin Nazemi, Summer 2005, "The study of relationship between earnings quality and stock returns with emphasis on the role of accrual figures in Tehran Stock Exchange". *Accounting and Auditing Review*, Year 12, No 40, PP. 37-60.
- iv. Rezaee and Ghenayinejad, Year 2012. "The Relationship between Transparency in Financial Reporting and Tax Avoidance with Value of Corporates". *Accounting Studies*. No.42.
- v. Salehi Amiri, Seyyed Reza and Seyyed Majid Motaharinejad. (2010). "Social Responsibility of Corporates and Stakeholders". *Research of Social Responsibility of Organizations* (2), Cultural and Social Research Group, The Expediency Discernment Council.
- vi. Arabmazar et. al. Spring 2011. "The Relationship between Financial Reporting Transparency and Tax Reporting in Iran". *Accounting Research*. 3rd Year, No. 9. PP. 22-37.
- vii. Mansourfar, Karim, 2006, *Statistic Methods*, Tehran University Publication, 5th Edition
- viii. Adhikari, A., Derashid, C., Zhang, H., 2006. Public policy, political connections, and effective tax rates: longitudinal evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy* 25, 574–595.
- ix. Akerlof, G., Michael Spence and Joseph Stiglitz . 1970. "Markets with
- x. Andrade. C. Sandro, Bernile. Gennaro,—Hood. M. Frederick 2009." *SOX*,
- xi. Armstrong, C.S., Core, J.E., Taylor, D.J., Verrecchia, R.E., 2010. When does information asymmetry affect the cost of capital? *Journal of Accounting Research*, Forthcoming.
- xii. Asymmetric information". At URL:<http://www.Nobelprize.Org\Economist>.
- xiii. Avi-Yonah, R.S., 2008. Corporate social responsibility and strategic tax behavior. In: Schn, W. (Ed.), *Tax and Corporate Governance*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg.
- xiv. Blouin, J., Balakrishnan, K. & W. Guay 2011, "Does Tax Aggressiveness Aeduce Financial Reporting Transparency?", University of Pennsylvania, Available at: <http://ssrn.com>
- xv. Chen, Y., Huang, S., Pereira, R., Wang J., 2009. Corporate tax avoidance and firm opacity, Working paper, Florida International University
- xvi. Corporate Transparency, And the Cost of Debt" *Journal of Financial*
- xvii. de Villiers, C., van Staden, C.J., 2011. Where firms choose to disclose voluntary environmental information. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*. <<http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/>
- xviii. Dechow, P., Dichev, I., 2002. The quality of accruals and earnings: The role of accrual estimation errors. *The Accounting Review*.
- xix. Desai, M., Dharmapala, D, 2006. Corporate tax avoidance and high powered incentives. *Journal of Financial Economics*.
- xx. Dyreng, S.D., Hanlon, M., Maydew, E.L., 2008. Long-run corporate tax avoidance. *The Accounting Review* 83 (1), 61–82.
- xxi. Economic—Consequences of Increased Disclosure: Evidence from
- xxii. Francis, J., LaFond, R., Olsson, P., Schipper, K., 2005. The market pricing of accruals quality. *Journal of Accounting & Economics*
- xxiii. Frank, M.M., Lynch, L., Rego, S., 2009. Tax reporting aggressiveness and its relation to aggressive financial reporting. *The Accounting Review*.
- xxiv. Freedman, J., 2003. Tax and corporate responsibility. *Tax Journal* 695 (2), 1–4.
- xxv. Freise, A., Link, S., Mayer, S., 2008. Taxation and corporate governance – The state of the art. In: Schn, W. (Ed.), *Tax and Corporate Governance*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg.
- xxvi. Friedman, M., 1962. *Capitalism and Freedom*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL
- xxvii. Gu, Z., Wu, J.S., 2003. Earnings skewness and analyst forecast bias. *Journal of Accounting & Economics*
- xxviii. *Intermediation*, Volume 18, Issue 4
- xxix. *International Cross-listings*. *Journal of Financial Economics*,
- xxx. Landolf, U., 2006. Tax and corporate responsibility. *International Tax Review* 29, 6–9.